

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW ON PITTADHARA KALA W.S.R TO MAHASROTAS (DIGESTIVE SYSTEM)**Dr. Ketan L. Tamhankar*¹, Dr. Sayali Saoji²**¹Assistant Professor, Department of Rachana Sharir MES Ayurved Mahavidyalaya, Khed, Maharashtra.²Assistant Professor in Rachana Sharir Department SNKD Trust Nallosopara Ayurved Medical College Nallosopara East.***Corresponding Author: Dr. Ketan L. Tamhankar**

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INTRODUCTION

Globally Ayurveda is on the top in this regard and is now considered as conventional medicine Anatomy is considered to be backbones of medical field. Without the knowledge of these branche one cannot be a successful medical practitioner. This stands true irrespective of the medical specialty, whether indigenous or cotemporary modern medical science.

Sushruta was the first to describe *Kala*. *Kala* is one of the most difficult topics to scientifically understand. Its importance lies in the fact that its integrity plays a crucial role for normal development from the time of conception to a fetus at term and then for normal growth and development from neonatal stage to adult human form and also keeping the individual healthy throughout the life. This means that it is required for nourishment of all cells of the body, controlled growth of various dhatus (body tissues) and Ashayas (organs) and replacement of senile cells. It is also important for repair in case of damage to specific parts of the body. However, the individual's genome, and its interaction with environment (ahar, vihar and aushadh) exert continuous influence on maintaining the harmony between dosha, dhatu and mala. Successful interaction results in healthy state while abnormal interaction results in initiation of pathophysiology. Healthy interaction between adjacent cells and later adjacent and/or distant tissues and organs results in formation of healthy cells of various types, tissues, organs and organs-system. *Kala* also need to remain in healthy form to keep the entire body healthy. However, when one or more of them deviates from their normal state the body suffers. Treating its pathology to bring the body back to normal state is very important, but the successful clinical application depends on the proper understanding of *Kala*.

Need of study

A few attempts have been made by the modern Ayurvedic researchers and experts to equate *Kala* with any structure, especially Pittadhara *Kala*. However, some of them have considered only one feature of Pittadhara *Kala* and that is of digestion; and leaving other functional criteria they have given the equivalent of this *Kala*. For example, pancreatic and hepatic cells, which produce pancreatic juice and bile, have been equated with Pittadhara *Kala*.

In the second chapter an attempt is made to fix what actually Mahasrotas means because after demarcating this one can discuss about Pittadhara *Kala*.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

- 1- To reveal the intent of Sushruta behind the derivation of *Kala Sharira*.
- 2- To reveal the relevance between the theory of *Pittadharakala* and the theory of Mahasrotas(Digestive system).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

– Various Samhita, review journals, pub article and thesis.

KALA AND ALLIED SUBJECTS IN MODERN ANATOMY

Sushrut was the first to describe *Kala Sharira* under Sharir Sankhya Vyakarana Adhyay of Shushruta Samhita; however, the description is in very much brevity. He has explained seven types of *Kalas* along with their short, but very significant definition. *Kala* is explained as an interface between Dhatu and Ashaya that provides a barrier between the two. *Kalas* are covering of layer of Shleshma (mucosa) or like sheets of a Snayu (membranous structure), or amniotic membrane (mucus).

कलाः खल्वपि हि सप्त भवन्ति धात्वाशयान्तर मर्यादाः
यथा हि सार काष्ठेषु छिद्यमानेषु दृश्यते ॥
तथाहि घातुमांसेषु छिद्यमानेषु दृश्यते ॥
स्नायुभिश्च प्रतिच्छन्नान् सन्ततांश्च जरायुणा ॥
श्लेष्मणा वेष्टितांश्चापि कलाभागांस्तु तान् विदुः ॥

(सु. शा. 4/5-7)

Like the Saara (pith) of wood is visible on its cross section (or longitudinal section); similarly, *Kala* is visible on dissection of Dhatu, Mamsa etc. Coverings of Snayu, proper encasing (of the fetus) by Jarayu and coverings by Shleshma are *Kalas*. *Kala* is Antara

This means that *Kalas* are pliable structures. All the three structures (examples) may or may not necessarily be present in each and every *Kala*, even one or two of the above-mentioned structures may be found existing in the *Kalas*.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Description of *Kala* in Sushruta Samhita *Kala* in *Sharirasthana*

Maryada (boundary) between Dhatu and Ashaya; in other words, it provides an interface (barrier) between Dhatu and Ashaya. Its existence is inferred by its function; that is of supporting the relevant Dhatu.

दधति इति धातवो रसरक्तमांसादयः, कफपित्तपुरीषाणि अपि प्राकृतानि स्वकर्मणा दधति इति धातवः, तेषां आशया अवस्थानप्रदेशा धात्वाशयाः, तेषां अन्तरेषु मर्यादाः सीमाभूता इति अर्थः ॥ तासां अन्तःस्थितत्वेन अप्रत्यक्षाणां अस्तित्वं प्रति उपमानं प्रमाणं निर्दिशन् आह-भवत इत्यादि। एतेन कला स अधिष्ठान पृथग्धातु उपलम्भ कार्येण अव्यक्तं एव कलानां अस्तित्वं साधितं भवेत्। तासां उपष्टम्भकं निर्दिशन् आह-स्नायुर्भिः इत्यादि। सन्ततान् सम्यक् प्रकारेण व्याप्तान्। जरायु उल्बाकारो येन वेष्टिताः प्राणिनो जायन्ते; कलावेष्टको अपि तद्वत् एव।

(सु. शा. 4/5-7 पर डल्हण)

दधन् = to hold

Dalhana's commentary explains this in some detail. Rasa, Rakta etc. hold (support) the body and hence they are called Dhatus. Similarly, Kapha, Pitta and Purisha also support body when they are in their normal status, so they are also called Dhatus. The sites of their location are called Ashayas. Boundary between these Dhatus and

their Ashayas are called *Kalas*. Since they are located within the body their existence is explained by simile. The *Kala* with its location supports different Dhatu so their existence is proven though it is invisible (in an intact body). For example, Snayu etc. support (the body). Encasing by *Kala* is similar to amnion covering the fetus.

षष्ठी पित्तधरा; या चतुर्विधमन्नपानमामाशयात् प्रच्युतं पक्वाशयोपस्थितं धारयति।

(सु. शा. 4/18)

पित्तमत्रान्तरग्निस्त्रयसंज्ञकम्। आमाशयात् प्रच्युतं कफाशयात् भ्रष्टं, पक्वाशयोपस्थितं पक्वाशयगमनायोपस्थितं पित्तस्थानं संप्राप्तं, धारयति 'पाकार्थ' इति शेषः। तथा च संग्रहः-“षष्ठी पित्तधरा नाम पक्वामाशयमध्यस्था। सा ह्यन्तरग्नेरधिष्ठानतयाऽऽमाशयात् पक्वाशयोन्मुखमन्नं बलेन विधार्य पित्ततेजसा शोषयति पचति” (अ.सं. शा.अ. 5) इति ॥

(सु. शा. 4/18 पर डल्हण)

Description of Kala in Ashtang Hridaya

Sixth *Kala* is *Pittadhara*, which retains the consumed food (of four types) for further digestion, which oozes from *Amashaya* and is heading towards *Pakwashaya*. *Pitta* is *antar Agni*. *Amashaya* is explained as

षष्ठीं पित्तधरा नाम पक्वमाशयमध्यस्था । सा ह्यन्तरग्नेरोधिष्ठानतयाऽऽमाशयात्
पक्वमाशयोन्मुखमन्नं बलेन विधार्य पित्ततेजसा शोषयति पचति पक्वं च मुंचति दोषाधिष्ठिता तु
दौर्बल्यादाममेवाततोऽसावन्नस्य ग्रहणात् पुनर्ग्रहणीसंज्ञा । बलं च तस्याः पित्तमेवाग्न्यभिधानमतः
साऽग्निस्तद्धोबृंहितैकयोगक्षेमा शरीरं वर्तयति ।

(अ.सं. शा. 5/36)

षष्ठी पक्वामाशययोर्मध्ये स्थिता आमाशयात् पक्वमाशयोन्मुखमन्नं बलेन विधार्य पचति ।
पित्ततेजसा करणभूतेन । सैव वातादिदोषाधिष्ठानेन दौर्बल्यादामामेव विमुञ्चति यदेवाग्नेर्धारणं
तदेव तस्या उपस्तम्भनम् । यदेवाग्नेरुपबृंहणं तदेवास्या उपबृंहणमित्येकयोगक्षेमा ॥

(अ.सं. शा. 5/36पर शशीलेखा)

Sixth *Kala* is *PittadharaKala*. It is situated between *Amashaya* and *Pakwashaya*. It is site for *Antargni* (*Jatharagni*) so it (forcefully) retains food that has been released from *Amashaya* and is proceeding towards colon, and digests it with *Teja* of *Pitta* and then releases

the digested food. It is the site of *Vata* etc. *Doshas*. Its weakness (in holding the chyme for sufficient time) results in release of *Ama* (partly digested food) so maintenance of *Agni* would hold it (function of *Grahani*).

Description of Kala in Ashtang Hridaya

धात्वाशयान्तरक्लेदो विपक्वः स्वस्वमूष्मणा ॥

श्लेष्मस्त्रायवपराच्छन्नः कलाख्यः काष्ठसारवत् । ताः सप्त ---- ।

(अ.ह. शा. 3/9)

PittadharaKala: It is located in (directed towards) *Pakwashaya* where the *Agni* is situated. With *Teja* of *Pitta* it desiccates, digests and then leaves the food. If it is vitiated by any *Dosha* it leaves undigested food and

gets the name of *Grahani*. Strength of *Agni* is its strength. Favored and nurtured by strength of *Agni* it supports the body.

Description of Kala in Bhavaprakasha

स्नायुभिश्च प्रतिच्छन्नान् सन्ततांश्च जरायुणा ।

श्लेष्मणा वेष्टितांश्चापि कलाभागांस्तु तान् विदुः ॥

धात्वाशयान्तरे धातोर्यः क्लेदस्त्वधितिष्ठति ।

देहोष्मणाभिपक्वश्च सा कलेत्यभिधीयते

(भा.प्र. पू. 3/216-217)

Bhavamishra's opinion about *Kala* is almost same as that of *Sushruta* and *Vagbhat*; only difference is the specificity made about *Kleda* and *Ushma*. He has deviated from his predecessors by specifically stating

that the *Kleda* involved is of *Dhatu* (located in *Ashaya*) and its maturation to the form of *Kala* is achieved by the action of body heat.

Description of Kala in Sharangdhara

मांसासृग्मेदसां तिस्रो यकृत्प्लीहनोश्चतुर्थिका ।
 पञ्चमी च तथाऽन्त्राणां षष्ठी चाग्निधरा मता ॥
 रेतोधरा सप्तमी स्यादिति सप्त कलाः स्मृताः ॥६॥

(शा. पू. 5/6)

There is no difference between what other ancient scholars have described and commentators on Sharangdhara have described. Adhamalla has clarified that order of Mamsadhara and Raktadhara is altered due to the support Mamsa is giving to Raktadhara Kala (located in it) and their mutually favoring to each other.

Modern perspective of kala

PittadaraKala: This Kala forcefully retains the food (partly digested) which is heading towards Pakwashaya, digests it and desiccates by the action of (Teja of) Pitta

and then propels it further. This description is sufficient to understand that this could be mucosa of duodenum, jejunum and ileum (figures 3.1.11 to 3.1.13). Two types of movement are observed in small intestine viz segmentation (bidirectional movement i.e. simultaneous forward and backward movement by cutting method) and propulsion in unidirectional i.e. forward movement. Forceful retention appears to be segmentation, which mechanically aids in digestion by way of cutting and mixing.

Figure 3.1.12 (left): *PittadaraKala* where the lumen on dissection looks like longitudinal section of a stem of plant as shown in left lower corner.

Figure 3.1.13 (right): The image shows different parts of duodenum with lumen in both the ends resembling cross section of a stem of a plant.

Figure 3.1.14: Three-dimensional explanation of anatomical location of *Pittadara Kala* according to *Bhavamishra (B.P. Pu.Kha. 3/211-213)*

PittadaraKala provides a barrier between luminal content of the small intestine and its internal milieu (tissues). The hostile factors that have entered the small intestinal lumen include high acidity of chyme (in the duodenum near pyloric sphincter), dietary antigens, microorganism, toxins, drugs etc. Proper digestion and absorption of dietary nutrients take place after overcoming all these hostilities. The healthy status of *PittadaraKala* is also essential for both of these functions. Functional Anatomy of *Kala*.

Function of *PittadaraKala* is to protect the Ashaya from its own digestion, digest and desiccate the food and through neuronal control regulate the GIT movement. This means that during the formation of Mahasrotas the *Pittadara* interacts with local part of Mahasrotas and develops different structure than that of Amaqshaya or Pakwashaya. That is the reason *PittadaraKala* and Purishadhara *Kala* are mentioned differently.

The description of *Kala* very minimal, but by no means very vague considering the time of evolution of Ayurveda and facilities available in those times. Help of modern anatomy and physiology makes the subject matter easier; and then by analyzing the description of physiologic anatomy following functions of *Kala* emerge.

- Providing support to the Ashayas (organs)
- Providing barrier between Dhatus and their Ashayas and there by providing protection to the Ashayas as is found with *Kala* in Ama-Pakwashaya. For example, digestive system digests the muscles in mutton, but does not digest the muscles of gastrointestinal tract.
- Resemblance of *Pittadara* and Purishadhara *Kala* with star-shaped lumen means that the surface area of *Kalas* increases and that enables them to function more efficiently in relation to digestion, absorption and production of waste (by absorbing the nutrients, water and electrolytes).
- Barrier function is extended to brain as well as fetus also.
- Simile to pith of plant (on section) means that *Kala* provides nutrition (including water and electrolytes) to the tissue where it is located
- Simile for oozing from *Kala* on injury like oozing from the incision on the lactiferous plant also means that *Kala* helps in repairing the tissue damage.

Digestion of food e.g. *PittadaraKala*

- Absorption (of nutrient from the gastrointestinal tract) after digestion of food
- Propulsion of chyme in *Pittadara* and Purishadhara *Kalas*
- Providing nourishment to the relevant part of the body or whole body e.g. *PittadaraKala* provides

nutrition to the body after absorption of nutrients, water and electrolytes etc.

- Providing strength (and cushion-effect) to adjacent structure such as Shleshmadhara *Kala* in bone joints
- Facilitation of ejaculation of Shukra (spread in whole body of a male) ultimately from penile urethra to exterior (of male body). Analysis of this statement with the help of modern anatomy and physiology reveals that this function is controlled by hypothalamus-pituitary-testicular axis. Since females also have seventh Dhatu i.e. Shukra for them it is hypothalamus-pituitary-ovarian axis. In other words, the endocrine hormones related to reproductive system function reaching the reproductive system also need *Kala*. Albeit, this *Kala* is already explained as Raktadhara *Kala*.

DISCUSSION

On the basis of information collected under review of literature, and the critical analysis as performed under the chapter of discussions, the derived conclusions are presented as under: After thorough study of *Kala* it is decided that it should be a tissue membrane as it separates each Dhatu from its Ashaya.

PittadaraKala is unequivocally the mucosa of small intestine. It starts from pyloric sphincter as the Acchhapitta secrete from there. Acchhapitta is Amla, clear and not solid (i.e. liquid). The chyme secreted from the pyloric sphincter is acidic. So Acchhapitta is chyme secreted from pyloric sphincter and hence *PittadaraKala* starts from pyloric sphincter. The function of *PittadaraKala* is to forcefully hold the chyme, digest it and then move it towards Pakwashaya. So *PittadaraKala* ends at Pakwashaya Dwar, which is ileocecal valve.

Only few views are available about what structure the *Kala* is.

- 1) Prof. Dr. D.G. Thatte has explained that the anatomical description of seven *Kala* is mostly of inner linings of the body cavities and not about outer serous, parietal or visceral covering having Mamsadhara *Kala*. Some are endothelial linings whereas some are facial sheaths between a particular tissue like Mamsa Dhatu. Many of these *Kala* give origin to muscle tissue like cremasteric fascia to cremasteric muscle or thoracolumbar fascia to muscles of posterior abdominal wall.
- 2) Acharya Sudarshana Shastri has stated that as per description found in Sushrut Samhita formation of all *Kalas* originally occurs from three primordial structures viz Snayu praticchhanna *kala* (fibrous membrane), jarayusantata *kala* (serous membrane) and Shleshma veshtita *Kala* (mucus membrane).^[2]
- 3) Prof. Dr. Sumati S. Khot has explained *kala* in an article titled "Basic Concept of *Kala* (Membrane)"

in the following manner. *Kalas* are minute particles present in the body which are concerned with the process of formation of the Dhatus and Malas. One of the meanings of *Kala* is quality and biologically active quality of one Dhatu giving birth to another type is termed as *Kala* by acharyas. These are membranes with special functions. We can correlate the *Kalas* structurally with fascia, septum, fibrous membrane; mucous membrane or serous membrane but functionally, we can correlate them with cells or formative elements.^[3]

CONCLUSION

Kala is one such subject, which is too concise to decipher and then apply its knowledge in clinical fields. Very few articles are available in this regards. Some modern Ayurvedic scholars have given their opinion about these *Kalas*. For example duodenum, pyloric orifice, small intestine or its mucosa, stomach and duodenum with their inner linings, etc. have been put forth as an equivalent of *PittadaraKala*. This has the potential to create confusion in the mind of young researchers and practitioners of Ayurveda. So an attempt has been made here to understand what is meant by *Kala* with application of modern anatomy and physiology. *Kala* is considered to be a barrier between Dhatu and its Ashaya. There are seven *Kalas*, but the topic of research is restricted to *Kala* related to Mahasrotas.

Entire research was focussed on the term *Kala* related to anatomy without deviating to other meanings of *Kala* as they do not serve any purpose for the advancement of knowledge of anatomy. General description of *Kala* is given in only two verses. In fact, only definition is given in one line of the verse and the remaining part is devoted to similes given for the explanation of *Kala*. So the term *Kala* is discussed at great length with the help of similes, embryogenesis given by commentator Indu on Ashtanga Samgraha and description of *Kala* in different ancient texts. An approach is adopted to understand this description in perspective of modern functional anatomy as the macroscopic or microscopic description of *Kala* is missing. A logical conclusion is drawn with all these discussions and then that conclusion is tested whether it can be applicable to all the seven *Kalas*. In the chapter titled "*Kala* and allied subjects in modern medicine" the anatomical structures for all the seven *Kalas* have been fixed without deviating from the basic definition of *Kala* and its function. At the end of the chapter even what structure would be representing the Shukradhara *Kala* is discussed as the ultimate aims of any research is to enhance the existing knowledge.

PittadaraKala the parts of Mahasrotas. Here an attempt is made to understand what is meant by Mahasrotas by considering the embryology and the synonyms along

with the description of clinical conditions where the term Mahasrotas has appeared.

PittadaraKala is discussed before discussing the Purishadhara *Kala* for the simple reason that the anatomically and physiologically this comes earlier. Digestion of food takes place first and then the faeces are formed. There is absolutely no anatomical description about this *Kala*. Its anatomical location according to various ancient scholars has been decided discussing about what should be considered as Shleshmasthan of Amashaya and Pittasthan of Amashaya. Grahani is said to be its synonym so the physiological anatomy is discussed here to exactly locate the *PittadaraKala*. Site and function of Agni (Grahani) are debated in chapter of *PittadaraKala*. The terms Vishishta Dhamani and Grahani Nadi appear in this relation and so they are discussed in details as they are crucial in deciding the exact location of *PittadaraKala*. Charaka's view about Acchhapitta creates some confusion whether the *PittadaraKala* ends where the Acchhapitta is secreted or it ends near Pakwashaya Dwar. Hence, this point has been discussed at length by considering various Paka (Bhavas) of digestion according to Ayurveda and also physiology of digestion according to modern physiologic anatomy of digestive system to conclude where the *PittadaraKala* ends. All the views have been reviewed and then a conclusion is drawn that the small intestinal mucosa should be considered as *PittadaraKala*. A short description of small intestinal mucosa and its functions is given. Finally, this conclusion is tested by comparing various clinical conditions involving *PittadaraKala* (Grahani) and mucus membrane and applying this knowledge in their clinical features and treatment.

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